

THE EFFECT OF YOGA ON PRISONERS: AN OVERVIEW**Mr. Akshit Saharan¹, Dr. Anindita Das², Dr. Vijay Kumar Singh³**¹Department of yogic science, Lakshmibai National Institute of Physical Education, Gwalior, Madhya Pradesh, India, email- akshitsaharan99@gmail.com, Ph No- 7976260265²Associate Professor, Lakshmibai National Institute of Physical Education, Gwalior, Madhya Pradesh, India, email- anindita416@gmail.com, Ph No- 7999673117³Assistant Professor, Department of Yogic science and Human Consciousness, Dev Sanskriti Vishwavidyalaya, Haridwar, Uttarakhand, India, email- vijaysinghdsuv@gmail.com**Corresponding author- Mr. Akshit Saharan****ABSTRACT**

There are evidences that yogic practices are beneficial for the overall mental and physical health of prisoners. However, there is a lack of an overview study focused on the effects of yogic practices on mental and physical health of prisoners. Thus, the aimed of the present overview study is to clarify the effects of yogic practices on mental and physical health of prisoners. I have reviewed total 300 research articles out of which 112 was selected for my study. Existing evidence concludes that yogic practices significantly impact on mental and physical health of prisoners. The studies was taken from Google scholar and PubMed.

Keywords:

Yoga; Yoga and Prisoner; Prisoner Mental health and Physical health; Prison Environment

INTRODUCTION

According to the most recent World Prison Population List, issued in December 2021, there may be more than 11.5 million inmates worldwide. Prison suicide rates worldwide are around three times higher in men and nine times higher in women than those in the general population (1), (2). Prisoners experience significant mental stress on a daily basis, as indicated by their rate of psychiatric morbidity. (3),(4). According to The Times Of India article Overcrowding, protracted incarceration of pre-trial convicts, unsatisfactory living circumstances, a lack of treatment programmes and staff, and charges of inhuman treatment by prison staff have all drawn the attention of critics throughout the years. (5),(6). These kinds of factors mainly responsible for mental and physical related problems in the prisoners. (7),(8),(9),(10),(11),(12). There are many health issues with the Prisoners but there are some issues from which most of the prisoners suffer.

Most common health problems for the Prisoners are: Depression and anxiety (13),(14), Sleep(15),(16) Antisocial behaviour and aggression (17),(Gibbon et al., 2020).(19), (20) etc. These all are one of the few mental health related issues from which the Prisoners all around the world are suffering. (4). Other than mental disorders there are many other physical and psychological problems such as violence (23),(24), sleep problems (25), (15), self-harm (26),(27), migraine headaches, profound fatigue, gastro-intestinal problems, poor appetite and weight loss, cardiovascular problems (28),(29).

Healthcare administrators and concerned government officials have taken notice of this phenomenon (30),(31), (32),(33),(34),(35),(36) who are now seeking solutions to these problems.

Given these presumptions, research suggests that yoga and other mind-body meditation practises offer some novel approaches that are scientifically proven to be efficient ways to improve the physical health, reduce stress, and improve mental health in inmates. (37),(38),(39).

Many studies worldwide proved that Inmates from many different countries are often reported to have high levels of psychiatric illness (40),(4) and there is a need of an alternative medicine to overcome these mental as well as physical health issues. So, the purpose of this study is to compile all of the available information on yoga as a method for managing and preventing overall ill-health in prisoners.

METHODOLOGY

PUBMED and Google scholar database were used for finding the researches. The selected Articles were published upto the year from 2002 to 2023. Keyword were selected through expert's Opinion and literature review. Using

Boolean logic, the following combination of Keyword was used in the search database “yoga” or “prisoner mental health and physical health” or “prison environment” or “yoga and prisoner”.

2.1. Mental Problems in Prisoners

Inmates from many different countries had often reported to have high levels of psychiatric illness. (40). The prison environment does play a key effect in the development of stress and psychological issues among jail inmates (41). Mental disorder are more common in prisoners than in the general population.(42) . Self-harm is a serious issue in the prison setting since inmates frequently engage in self-harm.(43).

2.2. Physical Problems in Prisoners

Modifiable risk factors for chronic diseases are encouraged by the prison environment (measured by length of incarceration), including poor diet and less sanitization(44). Compared to the normal population, prisoners are more likely to contract infectious diseases. (42).

- **Effect of yoga on Anxiety and Depression**

Many studies on yoga have shown that it significantly reduces melancholy and anxiety. (45),(46),(47),(48). Yoga lowered anxiety and depression in those with several conditions, including Parkinsons disease(49), cancer patient (50);(51), Breast cancer (52), rheumatoid arthritis(53), covid19 patients(54) as comparing with stretching and resistance training exercises. Yoga has successfully reduced the Depression and anxiety in children and adolescents(55), college students (56) as well as older adults (57),(58).

- **Effect of yoga on Sleep**

Yoga eliminates sleep-related issues like insomnia (59) and improves the sleep quality (60),(61),(62). Sleep problem is most common symptoms in any physical or mental problem and it can be improved by doing yoga such as during pregnancy (63), in Epilepsy disorder (64), in Cancer (65), Chronic respiratory disease (66), among Type 2 Diabetes patients(67) etc. Yoga enhances older person's quality of life and sleep patterns. (57).

- **Effect of yoga on Antisocial behaviour and aggression**

An individual suffering from antisocial personality disorder, generally referred to as sociopathy, consistently disregards right and wrong and appears careless with the needs and feelings of others. Individuals with antisocial personality disorder frequently manipulate, treat people brutally, or show a heartless indifference to their suffering. They don't feel sorry for themselves or regret what they did. Yoga can help among inmates (68), (69), (70), workers in workplace (71), (72), among adolescents (73) etc in removing Antisocial behaviour and reducing Aggression.

- **Effect of yoga on Violence**

In the World Report, the World Health Organization (WHO) makes this point quite apparent on Violence and Health: "Violence is a global scourge that tears apart the fabric of communities and threatens the lives, health and happiness of us all." Yoga reduce the violence in youth (80),(81), convicted extremist offenders (82), interpersonal violence (83). Thus, yoga helps in overcoming from violence behaviour in the people (84).

- **Effect of yoga on Migraine Headache**

Yoga can play a significant role in improving migraine problem and its related symptoms (85),(86),(87). Yoga helps in getting ease from headache in Migraine (88),(89),(88), in some researches yoga can be best option as a adjuvant therapy with other pharmacological therapy (90),(91),(92),(93).

- **Effect of yoga on profound fatigue**

A generalised sense of exhaustion or lack of energy is referred to as fatigue. Fatigue is something which comes mostly as a symptom in any one or more diseases or as a side effect of any medication such as chemotherapy (94),(95), (96). Yoga directly impact on the root cause of the fatigue and which further responsible for overcome fatigue such as the cancer (97),(51),(65), Chronic respiratory disease(66), Multiple sclerosis (98) etc.

- **Effect of yoga on Gastro intestinal disorder**

All the disorders which are related to GI Tract i.e., related to Oesophagus, Stomach, Intestine and Rectum. It includes diseases like Irritable bowel syndrome, Diarrhea, Ulcerative Colitis etc. Yoga directly effects on - Irritable bowel syndrome (99), inflammatory bowel disease (100),(101), Abdominal pain in gastrointestinal disorder (102), Ulcerative colitis (103),(104).

Effect of yoga on Prisoners

Compared to the general community, prisoners' levels of mental health issues, substance misuse, and poor physical health are much higher in prison environments.(105),(44),(41). Yet there are many researches which proved that Yoga could be a solution to all those problems (107), ,(109), (37). Yoga helps convicts become more mature, enhancing skills like their capacity to take responsibility, feel more meaningful, and be more accepting of themselves. It also helps decrease aggression and antisocial behaviour in prisoners., (110), (69), (111). Prisoners

who participated in a yoga programme in the facility reported an improvement in their psychological wellbeing, (111),(112),(39), overall Mental health status i.e.,(stress, depression, anxiety, psychiatric disorders etc) (113),(37), (114),(115),(116),(117),(38),(68) and moreover the rate of recidivism also decreased in the prisoners after releasing from prison (118), (119).

3. LITERATURE REVIEW

Author, Year	Type of study	Topic	Conclusion
S Willy-Gravley, J Beauchemin, P Pirie, A Gomes, E Klein, 2019	Experimental study	Yoga Practice May Increase the Character Maturity of Male Prison Inmates	Substantial impact on traits related to self-direction, including maturity, a sense of purpose, and a decline in aggressive antisocial conduct.
S Willy Gravley, J Beauchemin, P Pirie, A Gomes, E Klein , 2021	Experimental study	A Randomized Controlled Trial of Yoga with Incarcerated Females: Impacts on Emotion Regulation, Body Dissociation, and Warnings of Substance Relapse	Yoga can help female prisoners who are struggling with their mental health and drug addiction.
KM Auty, A Cope, A Liebling, 2017	Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis	A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis of Yoga and Mindfulness Meditation in Prison	Positive effects of yoga and meditation on psychological well-being and behavioural functioning
S Kovalsky, B Hasisi, N Haviv, E Elisha , 2020	Experimental study	Can Yoga Overcome Criminality? The Impact of Yoga on Recidivism in Israeli Prisons	Yoga may have an impact on recidivism, according to study findings, which are corroborated by the fact that prisoners who practised yoga while they were in jail had reduced recidivism rates after being released.
M Ramanathan, AB Bhavanani , M Trakroo , 2017	Experimental study	Effect of a 12-week yoga therapy program on mental health status in elderly women inmates of a hospice	Yoga helps convicts feel more purposeful and hopeful by reducing negative thinking and improving mental health.

H Harner, AL Hanlon, M Garfinkel., 2010	Experimental study	Effect of Iyengar Yoga on Mental Health of Incarcerated Women	The symptoms of depression and anxiety in convicts significantly decreased.
P Sureka, S Govil, D Dash, C Dash, M Kumar, V Singhal, 2014	Experimental study	Effect of Sudarshan Kriya on male prisoners with non- psychotic psychiatric disorders: A randomized control trial	An individual's anxiety, depression, positive wellbeing, general health, and overall positive general wellbeing are all improved by engaging in Sudarshan Kriya and related activities.
M Kaur, DR Kumar, 2016	REVIEW PAPER	EFFECT OF YOGA AND MEDITATION ON STRESS MANAGEMENT OF FEMALE PRISONERS IN DELHI	Improved mood, lessened stress, lessened psychological anguish, greater attention, and enhanced decision-making are all benefits of yoga and meditation.
VS Nanduri, R Ram, YPV Ashram, 2021	Experimental study	Effects of Yoga Prana Vidya intervention on psychological wellbeing and criminal attitude of under-trial prisoners	Following the session, there was a noticeably favourable improvement in psychological health and a decrease in criminal attitude indicators.
L Bartels, LN Oxman, A Hopkins, 2019	Experimental study	"I Would Just Feel Really Relaxed and at Peace": Findings from a Pilot Prison Yoga Program in Australia	Improvements in the levels of anxiety, sadness, self-esteem, goal-direction, negative affect, and non-acceptance are signs that prisoners have benefited from the programme.
G Hopkin, S Evans-Lacko, A Forrester, J Shaw, G Thornicroft,2018	Systematic Review	Interventions at the Transition from Prison to the Community for Prisoners with Mental Illness: A Systematic Review	Several studies have shown that yoga is beneficial for prisoners' physical, mental, and emotional well-being.

AC Bilderbeck, M Farias, IA Brazil, S Jakobowitz, C Wikholm,2013	Experimental study	Participation in a 10-week course of yoga improves behavioural control and decreases psychological distress in a prison population	Within prison populations, yoga may be useful in enhancing subjective wellness, mental health, and executive performance.
AC Bilderbeck, IA Brazil, M Farias,2015	Experimental study	Preliminary Evidence That Yoga Practice Progressively Improves Mood and Decreases Stress in a Sample of UK Prisoners	Prisoners who practise yoga report much lower levels of overall stress.
Y Danielly, C Silverthorne, 2017	Experimental study	Psychological Benefits of Yoga for Female Inmates	Yoga reduces some undesirable behaviours and perhaps even mental health issues, which helps both convicts and prison employees.
A Sfindla, P Malmström, S Torstensson, N Kerekes,2018	Experimental study	Yoga Practice Reduces the Psychological Distress Levels of Prison Inmates	Obsessive-compulsive disorder, paranoid thoughts, and somatization symptoms are all decreased by yoga in jail inmates.

RESULT

Many research was examined, and the findings indicated that Yoga had a favourable impact on the prisoners' physical and mental health. Research studies support the value of yoga in improving jail conditions.

CONCLUSION

Many studies have found that prisoners are more likely than the general population to experience issues with their mental and physical health, thus it was decided to assess the value of yoga for inmates. An increasing corpus of research indicates that prisoner therapies for physical and mental health issues can be very quickly successful. Not just as a therapy but it also reduces the rate of Recidivism in Inmates.

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